

"Studies on the Spectrochemical Properties of Some Transition Metal Complexes-III". Infrared Spectra of Some Divalent Transition Metal Lactates*

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The infrared absorption bands of lactic acid in the rock-salt region have been assigned by a study of its deuterated analogue, lithium salt and diethyl ester.

The spectra of its complexes with Cu (II), Co (II), Ni (II), Mn (II), Zn (II) and Cd (II) in the hydrated, dehydrated and deuterated forms have also been studied. It is observed that the hydroxyl stretching vibration is greatly perturbed by coordination to a metal ion. The maximum frequency shift from 3333 cm^{-1} in acid to 2550 cm^{-1} in copper(II) lactate is observed. The frequency of coordinated hydroxyl group is found to vary as $\text{Mn} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cu} < \text{Zn}$. The ionized carboxyl group stretching frequency is very little affected by the metal ion, which indicates a purely ionic bonding. A structure involving coordination of both carboxyl and hydroxyl groups of the lactate ion and of water molecules has been proposed for these complexes.

Very little information has been reported in the literature regarding the structure of transition metal complexes of hydroxy acids. In order to elucidate their nature a programme was undertaken to investigate their spectrochemical, thermal and magnetic properties. The present paper describes the results of our infrared spectroscopic investigation of manganese (II), cobalt (II), nickel (II), copper (II) and zinc (II) lactates in hydrated, dehydrated and deuterated forms. Since completion of our work in 1964¹ a paper² has appeared (1965) describing some spectral features of metal lactates although no detailed work has yet been reported. Spectro-structural studies of complexes of this type are believed to be of interest in view of the biological importance of this ligand.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparative: All complexes (and also the lithium salt) were prepared by using the appropriate metal carbonate and were purified by recrystallization from water. Their purity and composition were ascertained by carbon, hydrogen and metal analyses. Dehydration of the complexes was carried out by heating the finely powdered sample at 110° for 12 hours over P_2O_5 in vacuo. Deuteration was achieved by adding a small amount of heavy water to the dehydrated product. Lactic acid- d_2 was prepared by refluxing the acid with a ten fold excess of heavy water on a water-bath for an hour. Excess of water was then removed by distillation under reduced pressure. Spectral measurements were

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1. Ranade, A.G., "Spectrochemical Properties and Thermal Stabilities of some Transition Metal Complexes", M. Sc. Thesis, Bombay University, (1964).

2. Bolard, J., *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, 900.

made on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer Model 221 equipped with a sodium chloride prism and/or sodium chloride prism-grating assembly. The samples were dispersed in KBr disks, Nujol and hexachlorobutadiene mulls.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the spectrum of a complex in the region ($4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is essentially the spectrum of the ligand in which some of the vibrations are perturbed by the metal ion, the spectrum of lactic acid is discussed first. The assignments of infrared absorption frequencies have been made by the study of lactic acid- d_2 , lithium lactate and ethyl lactate. Spectra of lactic acid, lactic acid- d_2 and lithium lactate have been illustrated in fig. 1.

15.4X11

FIG. 1

The strong broad band centred at 3333 cm^{-1} is assigned to the hydroxystretching vibration as confirmed by its shift to 2575 cm^{-1} on deuteration. While the corresponding νOH band is found at 3420 cm^{-1} in ethyl lactate an appreciable lowering of this frequency (3150 cm^{-1}) is seen in lithium lactate.

X-ray crystallographic studies by Tavale *et al.*^{3(a)} of sodium α -ketobutyrate have shown that there are six short distances ($2.5 \pm 0.2\text{ \AA}$) between sodium atom and the

3. Tavale, S. S., Pant, L.M. and Biswas, A. B.,

(a) *Acta Cryst.*, 1963, 18, 566.

neighbouring oxygens, five of these belong to the carboxylic and the remaining belong to the keto group. Structure of sodium pyruvate is also similar^{3(b)}. It has been observed in our laboratory that $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ frequency of the keto group is at 1789 cm^{-1} in pyruvic acid and it is observed at 1708 cm^{-1} in sodium pyruvate. Accordingly, the lowering of νOH frequency may be ascribed to an interaction of the alcoholic oxygen with lithium ion in anhydrous lithium lactate. Recently, such a structure has been established in the case of lithium glycolate monohydrate⁴.

The 1280 cm^{-1} band of lactic acid may be assigned to δOH in plane vibration of the alcohol group, the corresponding OD vibration being observed at 918 cm^{-1} . However, the possible coupling of δOH with CH vibrations cannot be ruled out here. The 1124 cm^{-1} band which is very little affected by deuteration or salt formation, is assigned to $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ vibration.

COOH Group: The strong broad absorption pattern in $3100-2900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is known to arise from νOH vibrations of polymeric species⁵. A band at $\approx 3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed which on deuteration shifts to 2283 cm^{-1} . A broad absorption pattern with several sub-maxima in $2800-2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is found in lactic acid, which may be attributed to summation bands of $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ and δOH in plane vibrations, the intensity of which is enhanced by Fermi resonance⁶. The 1718 cm^{-1} band of lactic acid is assigned to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ vibration. In aliphatic acids corresponding band is found in $1725-1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region⁵. The bands at 1400 and 1280 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ and δOH in plane coupled modes, the corresponding vibrations with deuteration being found at 1300 and 1000 cm^{-1} . The 926 cm^{-1} band observed in lactic acid is attributed to δOH out of plane as it disappears on deuteration. However, the corresponding OD vibration could not be located in view of the enhanced background scattering.

Spectra of Complexes:

Water bands:—All the complexes are obtained as hydrated crystalline products from aqueous media and there is observed considerable overlapping near 3300 cm^{-1} and near 1600 cm^{-1} due to H_2O bands. As indicated by dehydration and deuteration studies (fig. II) bands in $3500-3150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and near 1650 cm^{-1} , are attributable to νOH and δOH vibrations respectively. In addition to these, Fujita *et al.*⁷ have observed bands in $1000-800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region when water is held in coordination. Since no bands $< 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which could be assigned to coordinated water molecules have been observed, it is concluded that water is not held very strongly⁷ in these structures.

The alcoholic OH group:—Very little information has been reported concerning the coordinated hydroxyl group. Aqueous solution studies of metal glycolates by Goulden⁸ indicate that the δOH in plane frequency (1275 cm^{-1} glycolic acid) is shifted to higher frequency (1390 cm^{-1}) upon coordination with the metal ion and that the intensity of this is

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4. Cotton, R. H. and Henn, D. E., *Acta Cryst.*, 1965, 18, 820.

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7. Fujita, J., Nakamoto, K. and Kobayashi, M., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 3963.

8. Goulden, J. D. S., *Spectrochim Acta*, 1960, 16, 713.

15.4 × 10.6
FIG. 2.

15.4 × 10
FIG. 3

proportional to the stability of the complex. The shifted frequency in the solid complexes has been found at 1485 cm^{-1} by Nakamoto and coworkers⁹. In our series of compounds we find this mode to be of little diagnostic value due to the overlapping by bands due to CH_2 and COO^- groups. In the deuterated complexes the δOD band (near 1100 cm^{-1}) overlaps with the $\nu\text{C-O}$ band.

Based on the lowering in frequency and splitting of $\nu\text{C-O}$ mode (1097 to 1080 cm^{-1} and 1063 cm^{-1}), Kirshner and Kiesling¹⁰ have proposed a structure for copper (II) tartrate trihydrate. This mode is also found to have very little analytical importance in our case because of the complex structure multiplicity of bands.

The νOH vibration in the various metal-lactate complexes is examined critically. This frequency is found to vary as:

$$\text{Mn (2740)} > \text{Co (2725)} > \text{Ni (2715)} > \text{Cu (2550)} < \text{Zn (2770)}$$

indicating that the Irving-Williams¹¹ order of relative stability is followed by the present series.

The carboxylate COO^- group:— The antisymmetric stretching frequency of the COO^- group is found at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes. This suggests that the extent of ionic (or partial covalent) interaction of the metal with the carboxylate oxygen is more or less the same in all these complexes.

Based on the results discussed above, a structure of the type is suggested for the bidentate complexes of lactic acid with Mn (II), Co (II), Ni (II), Cu (II) and Zn (II) ions.

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